

Application form: Open Science Infrastructure (2024) - full proposal

Section 1: Applicants

Name of the main applicant	Dr. Mauricio Garnier-Villarreal
Affiliation – institution	Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam
Affiliation – department	Sociology
Position	Assistant/associate professor (UD1)
End date of contract	permanent position
Guarantee needed & added yes/no/n.a.	n.a
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Name of the co-applicant	Dr. Marcos José Jiménez Henríquez
Affiliation – institution	Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam
Affiliation – department	Sociology
Position	Post-doc
End date of contract	31-02-2026
Guarantee added yes/no/n.a.	yes
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Section 2: Summary

Proposed project title	Fast estimation of classical and new latent variable models in R
Project duration (in months)	24 months

English public summary
<p>LATENT is a free, open-source R package for researchers to estimate statistical models with unobserved (latent) variables, which are widely used in social, behavioural, and health sciences. While existing software is either too expensive or too limited for the current research demands, LATENT combines fast and flexible estimation with a user-friendly interface, making it accessible and affordable to conduct complex analyses. We will extend LATENT with new modeling capabilities, documentation, tutorials and journal articles, supporting transparency, reproducibility, and accessibility in science. Thus, we will follow open science principles by building an efficient, open, sustainable, and community-owned alternative to commercial software.</p>
Word count EN-SUM (max 100): 100

Dutch public summary

LATENT is een gratis, open-source R-pakket waarmee onderzoekers statistische modellen met niet-geobserveerde (latente) variabelen, die veel gebruikt worden in sociale, gedrags- en gezondheidswetenschappen, kunnen schatten. Bestaande software is te duur of te beperkt voor de hedendaagse onderzoekseisen. LATENT combineert snelle en flexibele modelschatting met een gebruiksvriendelijke interface en maakt het eenvoudiger om complexe analyses uit te voeren. We gaan LATENT uitbreiden met nieuwe modelleer- en documentatiemogelijkheden, handleidingen maken en wetenschappelijke artikelen over transparantie, reproduceerbaarheid en toegankelijkheid in de wetenschap schrijven. LATENT ondersteunt het principe van open science door een efficiënt, duurzaam en gemeenschappelijk beheerd alternatief te bieden voor commerciële software.

Word count NL-SUM (max 100): 100

Section 3: Alignment with the scope of the call

3.1 Vision for the project and alignment with the aim of this call

Latent Variable Models (LVMs) are arguably one of the most powerful and flexible multivariate-statistical methods. They include **Structural Equation Modeling (SEM)**, **Item Response Theory (IRT)**, and **Mixture Modeling (MM)**, which are considered the cornerstone of many analyses in a variety of fields to investigate unobserved variables like psychological traits, political attitudes, and labour inequalities. However, commercial software for LVMs is expensive and closed-source, limiting their access for underfunded researchers, students, and institutions.

It is urgent to have a fast, robust and reliable open-source software for LVMs that follows the **open-science principles of inclusion, equal opportunity, transparency, reproducibility, and accountability**. We aim to develop **LATENT**, a free and open-source **R-package** for LVMs that significantly enhances the accessibility to cutting-edge statistical analyses across social, behavioural, educational, political, and health sciences.

By offering a fast, flexible, and open-source alternative to commercial software, LATENT empowers researchers to conduct LVMs without financial or technical barriers.

Word count SEC31 (max. 150): 150

3.2 User communities, challenges and needs

Current R-packages for LVMs are free and open-source but have **three limitations**: **(L1)**: They are specialized in one type of LVM, forcing users to learn a **different syntax and documentation** for each kind of model they need. **(L2)**: They are very **slow compared to commercial software**, making simulation research of new statistical methods challenging, especially with big data and complex models. **(L3)**: They **lack flexibility to support complex and customized models** that are necessary for the increasing demands of scientists, urging them to either purchase software or modify their research question.

This project aims to speed up the development of the **R-package LATENT** to overcome these limitations. First, LATENT offers an **integrated, open-source solution** that will support all the LVMs (e.g., SEM, IRT, MM) using a unified and user-friendly syntax **(L1)**. Second, its core functionality is written in C++, making it faster than commercial software **(L2)**. Third, users will be able to customize their models with a variety of parameter transformations, non-linear constraints, and mix of loss functions, leading to the discovery of new statistical techniques **(L3)**. These solutions will lower the technical and financial barriers of users, saving them time to focus on the advanced modeling capabilities of LATENT.

Word count SEC32 (max. 200): 200

3.3 Alignment of project with OS principles

LATENT is integrated in the free and popular **R-programming language**. It is built upon cutting-edge packages (e.g., **Rcpp**, **data.table**, **armadillo**, and **lavaan**), securing the safety and reproducibility of its functionality. All models and algorithms in LATENT will be **fully documented**, with user-friendly **tutorials for applied researchers** and technical explanations for **incoming developers and contributors**.

A **public forum (Discourse's platform)** will serve as the main hub for support, feedback, and **collaborative decision-**

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making. This way, other researchers can collaborate to LATENT by making requests and direct **contributions – rewarded by co-authorship**- that we will moderate for appropriate development. This will turn LATENT into a **community-owned tool**.

Furthermore, LATENT is hosted publicly on **GitHub** as a **free open-source software** under the **GPL-3 license**, ensuring that all users can access, inspect, modify, and redistribute the codebase as long as it remains free. Therefore, we will use **open protocols and standards** that encourage community contributions through open-issue tracking, discussions, and version control.

Additionally, all materials to be developed, including **datasets, scripts, tutorials, and open access publications** will be shared as educational resources through LATENT's documentation and the package's website.

This way, LATENT aligns with the core open-science principles of **inclusion, equal opportunity, transparency, reproducibility, and accountability**.

Word count SEC33 (max. 200): 200

Section 4: Feasibility

4.1 Project plan

The plan is described in **six Work Packages (WP)**:

WP1: Writing fast C++ code for estimating LVMs.

This WP represents the **core of the project**. We are already working on the package LATENT, obtaining a significant **improvement in estimation speed**. For instance, in a benchmark test comparing LATENT with the packages [EGAnet](#), [Turbofun](#)s, and [lavaan](#) to estimate polychoric correlations between 100 variables with 6 response categories and 2000 subjects, LATENT was 1.6 times faster than [EGAnet](#) and [Turbofun](#)s, and 8 times faster than [lavaan](#). **This exemplifies that LATENT outperforms other implementations written in high-performance languages** like C (EGAnet) and Fortran (Turbofun)s). Right now, LATENT includes Exploratory and Confirmatory Factor Analyses (SEM methods), and Latent Class Analysis (MM method). With this project, we are committed to cover all the remaining LVMs while maintaining such high-performance benchmarks. Specifically, we will add SEM, Exploratory SEM, Dynamic SEM, IRT, (Mixture) Hidden Markov Models, multi-stage estimation (e.g., Structural After Estimation), and random effects for all of these models.

WP2: Development of new extensions/flexible models.

We want LATENT to extend beyond the capabilities of other LVM software. Therefore, we will **add newly developed features** such as the possibility of fitting SEM models without convergence problems due to Heywood cases or nonpositive-definite covariance matrices. In the same way, we will also enable the estimation of polychoric correlations that are positive-definite, avoiding the need for ad-hoc smoothing algorithms. Additionally, the model definition of any LVM will be made as flexible as possible, so the user may set parameter transformations, non-linear constraints, and equality and inequality constraints in any part of the model, fulfilling the necessities of the most complex research designs. **WP1 and WP2 will be done by the co-applicant, supervised by the main applicant.**

WP3: Implementation of a user-friendly interface.

A major limitation of current LVM packages is the use of different syntax formats. To ease the user-interface, we will use and expand on **lavaan's syntax**, since it is the most used package for SEM in R and there exists an ecosystem of packages around it. This way, LATENT will be able to **borrow from the work that has been already done** in lavaan and will stay compatible with the remaining packages that belong to the **lavaan's ecosystem**. This follows the open science principle of not re-doing work that has been done in other open-source software. **The main applicant will lead the efforts on WP3, working closely with the co-applicant.**

WP4: Writing technical documentation.

We will develop **comprehensive technical documentation** of the models and estimation methods implemented in LATENT. This will be published on GitHub and the package's website, improving on the transparency that is currently **lacking in commercial software**. This transparency will **boost the confidence of the users** in the functionality of the package. Furthermore, it will foster the engagement of the users in technical discussions and contributions, helping to create a long-term support for LATENT.

WP5: Production of tutorials.

A requirement for the widespread use of a new package is **user-friendly tutorials**. As we have the ambitious aim of implementing many LVMs, we will develop a variety of tutorials explaining their application and interpretation. These will be available as **tutorial papers in open-access academic journals**, as well as online **case-studies** for specific model applications-just like the R package [lavaan](#) includes "Basic" and "Examples/details" on its website. All the materials used in the tutorials will be accompanied with **proper citations and references** in line with **DORA principles**.

WP6: Collaborations and dissemination

First, once a year **the co-applicant will travel for one month to visit another developer to code in collaboration with them**. The first visit has been arranged with [Prof. Yves Rosseel](#) (developer of lavaan), to learn from his experience developing lavaan and how to integrate LATENT within the lavaan structure. Secondly, each member will do 2 trips a year to promote the package. These trips will encompass **presentations or workshops at international conferences**. We seek to present LATENT at methodological and applied conferences. In the methodological conferences (e.g., **IMPS and EAM**) we aim to reach users and contributors while in applied conferences (e.g., **APS and NCME**) we aim to reach applied researchers in areas such as social, behavioural, and educational sciences. **WP4, WP5, and WP6 will be carried out by both researchers.**

Project Schedule

WP	Year 1		Year 2	
	Semester 1	Semester 2	Semester 3	Semester 4
1	✓	✓	✓	✓
2		✓	✓	✓
3	✓	✓	✓	
4		✓	✓	✓
5			✓	✓
6	✓	✓	✓	✓

Word count SEC41 (max. 750): 747

4.2 Team composition

Name, surname	Affiliation	Expertise	Role/contributions
Mauricio Garnier-Villarreal	VU	Methodological researcher with experience developing new data analysis methods (here and here). Contributor of R packages (semTools , tidySEM , blavaan). He has written multiple online tutorials (here and here). Ample experience teaching and working with applied researchers as part of his appointments in Psychology, Nursing, and Sociology departments. He holds a clear view of how researchers use statistical software and what are the needs to be successful in their research.	<p>Project leader, methodologist, and programmer. He will lead the current development of LATENT and the dissemination plan.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LATENT planning: He oversees the prioritization of features in LATENT to ensure that high-priority features are developed first, while designing a structure that supports more advanced models. • User-friendly interface: He works on the implementation of the user-friendly interface of LATENT, based on lavaan's syntax. • Development of Advanced Statistical Models: He develops new models/features that can be added in LATENT. • Dissemination and Outreach: He promotes LATENT through peer-reviewed journal articles, tutorials, workshops, and conference presentations, ensuring broad visibility and adoption within the scientific community.

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • User Support and Community Engagement: He provides direct support to users via LATENT’s forum and GitHub, answering technical questions, guiding model usage, and incorporating feedback into future development.
Marcos Jiménez Henríquez	VU	<p>Specialized in programming, linear algebra, and LVMs. Focused on the development of new methods for SEM (e.g., here and here), he also has experience in Computational Thinking Tests in education. Author of the LATENT package, a project from his PhD.</p> <p>His combined technical and theoretical efforts ensure that LATENT remains a cutting-edge, sustainable open-source software for LMV.</p>	<p>Developer and maintainer of LATENT. His contributions include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implementation of High-Performance Algorithms: He leads the implementation of fast and modern optimization algorithms in C++, ensuring that LATENT can handle large datasets and complex models. • Development of Advanced Statistical Models: He implements new statistical models that meet the increasing methodological demands in the social sciences. His work expands the capabilities of existing LVMs and provides tools not currently available in other open-source software. • Dissemination and Outreach: Same as the project leader. • User Support and Community Engagement: Same as the project leader.

Word count SEC42 (max. 350): 350

4.3 Risk management

Risk	Likelihood and impact	Risk mitigation strategy
Difficulty ensuring compatibility across platforms (i.e., Windows, Linux, macOS)	Likelihood: low Impact: medium	Using Windows, Linux, and macOS virtual machines through GitHub Actions to check the compatibility of LATENT across these platforms.
Dependency changes in R or external packages (e.g., Rcpp, data.table, armadillo, and lavaan)	Likelihood: low Impact: low	Updating R packages regularly and running tests of LATENT with the latest R version.
Delays in the implementation and documentation of models due to their technical complexity	Likelihood: medium Impact: medium	Consulting experts in the open science and latent variable modeling community—such as Yves Rosseel (developer of <i>lavaan</i>)—to seek guidance.
Limited community engagement or user adoption	Likelihood: low Impact: high	Promoting LATENT through tutorials, workshops, and conference presentations , publishing peer-reviewed articles that make use of LATENT, integrating LATENT into lavaan's ecosystem to achieve long-term relevance and support , and

		incentivizing contributors with co-authorship , so that LATENT becomes a community-owned software .
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Word count SEC43 (max. 150): 150

4.4 Budget

Position	HOT scale	Institution	Total FTE	Years active	Amount
Marcos José Jiménez Henríquez: postdoc, programmer, psychometrician	HOT 2.1 - 10	VU	1,60	2	€ 140.920,00
Mauricio Garnier-Villarreal: project leader, programmer, psychometrician	HOT 2.1 - 13	VU	0,70	2	€ 92.953,00

Material/IT Type	Description	Cost calculation	Total (€)
(international) travel and accommodation expenses incl. conference visit	(1) international conferences to present the package. (2) teach workshops about the package. (3) work with collaborators in Brazil, Belgium, or the US	2000 per travel for 2 years, 4 trips per year	€ 16.000,00

Total Personnel requested: 233.873€

Total Material/IT requested: 16.000€

Total budget requested: 249.873€

4.5 Budget justification

Time allocation

The budget will cover **0.80 FTE for the main programmer** (Jiménez Henríquez), and **0.35 FTE for the project leader** (Garnier-Villarreal). The rest of their FTE will be covered by the Sociology Department at VU. This work time will be spent on the development of LATENT, expanding the documentation, writing tutorials, designing the website and Discourse forum for user-support and contributions, and writing academic papers for disseminating the new methods implemented in LATENT.

Dissemination

The grant will also cover four travel expenses per year for **attending applied and methodological conferences**, where the team will showcase LATENT and engage with both methodological and applied research communities. This is crucial to attenuate the risks. In the methodological conferences (e.g., IMPS and EAM) we will reach users and contributors. While in applied conferences (e.g., APS and NCME) we will reach applied researchers in areas like social, behavioural, and educational sciences. These expenses will result in **workshops and presentations to promote LATENT's features**. These activities are essential for **minimizing the risk related to low community engagement and user adoption**.

Collaboration

One trip a year will be used to work in collaboration other programmers, the first visit has been planned with [Prof. Yves Rosseel](#).

Word count SEC 45 (max. 200): 200

4.6 Impact plan

LATENT will enhance the efficiency, accessibility, and transparency of latent variable modeling by offering a fast, flexible, well-documented, and open-source alternative to commercial software. This will empower researchers to conduct advanced analyses without financial or technical barriers. We aim to reach researchers at different levels, like PhDs, professors, methodologists, statisticians, and consultants, to create a diverse and inclusive **community of users that actively asks questions, submit requests, and make technical contributions**. This endeavour aligns with the inclusion and accountability principles of open science.

The package will also serve as an **educational resource, improving statistical literacy and fostering methodological innovation** through comprehensive tutorials and detailed documentation.

To measure this impact, we will track CRAN downloads, citations, number of packages that depend on LATENT, participation in workshops, activity in the Discourse forum, and contributions made on GitHub.

In the long term, we expect that LATENT becomes a reference tool in methodological training, course curricula, and applied research workflows. If this endeavour is accomplished, faculty, students, and institutions will also benefit financially, as adopting LATENT reduces or eliminates the need to purchase costly commercial software licenses.

Word count SEC46 (max. 200): 183

Section 5: Sustainability and software management

Section 5.1: Sustainability plan

We are committed to ensure the **long-term sustainability** of LATENT beyond the initial funding period, making it part of our long-term workload. The project leader already has a permanent position at the VU and will **add the maintenance of LATENT as part of his work**. The co-applicant will **pursue a permanent academic position** at the conclusion of the project, with his prospects closely **tied to the research outputs and methodological developments achieved through LATENT**. Since LATENT is the core focus of his PhD, it will continue to serve as his **primary platform for implementing and publishing new statistical methods**, reinforcing the cutting-edge scientific sustainability of the project.

LATENT will also be integrated into the **lavaan ecosystem**, increasing its long-term relevance and support within this broad statistical community. We have already established collaborations with several R developers—serving as named contributors in some cases—which facilitates the seamless integration and collaboration of LATENT with related packages. Furthermore, by **acknowledging the co-authorship of contributors and new developers**, LATENT aims to become a **community-owned tool** in such a way **that does not depend on few maintainers**, a common issue in both free and commercial software.

To achieve this community-level status, we will ensure the long-term **visibility of the package** through peer-reviewed publications, online tutorials, conference presentations, workshops, and active involvement in the online discussion group. In addition, we will adopt **open governance practices**—such as community voting on major development directions—to **encourage participation and shared responsibility** for the package’s evolution.

Finally, we will seek additional funding opportunities (e.g., Veni) to support further development. Collaborations with other research teams that actively use LATENT may also serve as a source of funding, as they may be willing to invest in the implementation of features aligned with their methodological needs.

Word count SEC51 (max 300): 295

Section 5.2: Software management plan

1. Please provide a brief description of your software, stating its purpose and intended audience.

LATENT is an R package designed to estimate a wide range of **latent variable models (LVMs)** commonly used in the **social, political, educational, clinical, and behavioral sciences**. Initially developed during the PhD research of Marcos Jiménez to implement novel models with complex hierarchical constraints not supported by existing software, LATENT has evolved into a more comprehensive and general-purpose LVM toolkit.

Currently, LATENT supports **Latent Class Analysis (LCA)**, **Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA)**, and **Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA)**, offering features such as model fit indices, hypothesis testing, and advanced plotting and reporting tools. The package is under active development to expand its capabilities to include **(Mixture) Hidden Markov Models (HMM)**, **(Exploratory) Structural Equation Modeling (ESEM/SEM)**, and **(Multidimensional) Item Response Theory (MIRT)**, which are the most common **latent variable frameworks** encountered in applied research.

One of the most distinctive features in LATENT is its **unified syntax interface**, based on the popular lavaan syntax, which allows users to seamlessly specify and estimate different LVMs without switching between packages or learning multiple interfaces. This positions LATENT as a unique and user-friendly open-source solution for researchers who need flexibility, transparency, and computational efficiency in latent variable modeling.

Its primary audience includes applied researchers, data analysts, and methodologists across disciplines who require powerful latent variable tools that are **free, reproducible, and efficient**, in line with the principles of **open science**.

A second distinctive feature of LATENT is that all its optimization algorithms and statistical models are implemented from scratch in C++. The reason for this is that no package, either in R or C++, offers modern optimization techniques that makes possible the estimation of complex models with nonlinear parameter constraints, which are required by the increasing model complexity in the social sciences.

2. How will you manage versioning of your software?

We will follow **Semantic Versioning (SemVer)** principles to manage the versioning of LATENT library. Each release will be versioned in the format **MAJOR.MINOR.PATCH**:

- MAJOR version increases will indicate major rewrites in the package with respect to the previous stable version, like when a new statistical framework is incorporated (e.g., Item Response Theory) with their own lavaan-like syntax and print, summary, and plot functions.
- MINOR version increases will add new functionality that is compatible with the existing statistical frameworks that are already in LATENT (e.g., new estimators, nonlinear constraints, modeling capabilities, auxiliary functions to display results, etc).
- PATCH version increases will be used for bug fixes and code optimization.

This strategy aligns with open science principles by ensuring **transparency, reproducibility, and accountability**, while making it easier for users to track changes, cite software appropriately, and contribute to development.

Currently, the first version of LATENT has been released under the number version 0.1.0.

Versioning will be tracked using Git, and all releases will be tagged accordingly. We will also use a NEWS.md file to document changes for each version.

3. How will you make your software publicly available? What licence will your software have?

LATENT will be made publicly available through two main channels:

- **Development versions** will be hosted on **GitHub**, allowing users to access the most recent features, report issues, and contribute to the project during its active development. Each release will follow semantic versioning and include detailed documentation.
- **Stable versions** will be submitted to **The Comprehensive R Archive Network (CRAN)**, the official and widely used repository for R packages. Submission to CRAN ensures that each release meets rigorous standards for software quality, documentation, and compatibility across platforms.

LATENT will be released under the **GNU General Public License v3 (GPL-3)**. This license ensures that the software remains **free and open-source**, allowing users to use, modify, and redistribute the package, provided that any derivative work remains under the same license. This licensing choice supports the principles of open science by promoting transparency, collaboration, and long-term accessibility.

4. How will users of your software be able to cite your software?

Users of LATENT will be able to cite the software in two ways:

1. We plan to publish a **peer-reviewed article** that provides an overview and tutorial of the package. This publication will serve as the primary reference and citation for academic use, ensuring proper credit for the methodological contributions and facilitating traceability in scholarly work.
2. In addition, once LATENT is available on **CRAN**, users will be able to retrieve the recommended citation using R's native `citation()` function:

```
citation(package = "latent")
```

To cite package 'latent' in publications use:

Jiménez M, Garnier-Villarreal M, Franco VR, Abad FJ, Garcia-Garzon E, Garrido

LE (2025). latent: An R package for Latent Variable Modeling. R package version 0.1.0. <https://github.com/Marcosjnez/latent>.

A BibTeX entry for LaTeX users is

```
@Manual{,
  title = {latent: latent: An R package for Latent Variable Modeling},
  author = {Marcos Jiménez and Mauricio Garnier-Villarreal and Vithor R. Franco and Francisco J. Abad and Eduardo Garcia-Garzon and Luis E. Garrido},
  note = {R package version 0.1.0},
  url = {https://github.com/Marcosjnez/latent},
}
```

ATTENTION: This citation information has been auto-generated from the package DESCRIPTION file and may need manual editing, see ‘help("citation")’.

As it can be seen, this function automatically provides a formatted reference (e.g., in APA style), which includes author information, package version, and the CRAN URL, making it easy to cite LATENT in academic publications, reports, and teaching materials. In the future this automatic citation will include the academic papers, as well as the software manual.

This dual approach ensures both academic recognition and practical ease of use, aligned with open science and software citation best practices.

5. How will your software be documented? Please describe your plans for: user documentation, documentation for future developers and for installation requirements. Please provide links to documentation if already available.

The LATENT package will provide comprehensive documentation tailored to two types of users: applied and methodological researchers (users), and future developers.

For users, each function in LATENT will include structured documentation accessible via R’s built-in help system. This documentation will follow a consistent format:

- **Title:** Clear and concise description of the function.
- **Description:** Summary of the function's purpose.
- **Usage:** Syntax and explanation of all function arguments.
- **Details:** In-depth information on model specification, identification and estimation, interpretation of parameters, and guidance for handling issues such as non-convergence or improper solutions.
- **References:** Relevant journal publications and theoretical foundations.
- **Examples:** Reproducible code examples using real or simulated data to demonstrate the function’s application.

A comprehensive PDF manual is already available via the GitHub repository:

https://github.com/Marcosjnez/latent/blob/master/latent_0.1.0.pdf

On the other hand, to support future contributors and maintainers, LATENT will include a developer guide that outlines:

- The overall architecture and modular structure of the package.
- Explanations for adding new models, parameter constraints, and features.
- Guidelines for writing C++ code integrated via Rcpp.
- Clear instructions on how to compile the package and run the build process.

With regards to the installation of the software, we already provide [instructions for installation](#).

Dependencies (i.e., Rcpp, data.table, armadillo, and lavaan) will be listed in the package DESCRIPTION [file](#) and automatically managed through R’s package installation tools.

We plan to build a dedicated website similar to the one developed for the [blavaan](#) package, to which the project leader also contributes. *6. How will contribution guidelines and governance structure of your software be documented?*

The LATENT package is structured into distinct, modular components that facilitate collaboration and ensure maintainability. These components are organized into the following core modules, implemented in C++ and integrated with R via Rcpp:

- **Transformations:** Compilation of functions (e.g., log, exp, logit, softmax, etc) to transform the parameters and compute their respective jacobian.
- **Estimators:** Contains model-specific functions such as log-likelihoods, gradient vectors, and Hessian matrices that are necessary for the optimization algorithms.
- **Manifolds:** Encodes nonlinear constraints required by different model specifications (e.g., simplex, unit vectors, orthogonal matrices, etc).
- **Optimization Algorithms:** Includes methods such as gradient descent, Newton and pseudo-Newton approaches, and Expectation-Maximization.

Each header file within these modules includes standardized metadata at the top of the file:

```
/*
 * Author: Marcos Jimenez
 * email: m.j.jimenezhenriquez@vu.nl
 * Modification date: 03/02/2025
 */
```

This information provides transparency in authorship, supports traceability, and facilitates accountability in collaborative development. Additionally, the code is thoroughly commented to explain the role of functions, objects, and algorithmic steps, helping new developers understand and extend the code.

A **developer guide** (in progress) will be provided via the GitHub repository and LATENT's webpage. This guide will include:

- A high-level overview of LATENT's architecture and modules (i.e., transformations, manifolds, estimators, and optimization algorithms).
- Coding style conventions and documentation standards.
- Instructions for contributing new models or optimization techniques.
- Instructions for contributing new functions in LATENT and how to document them.
- Testing procedures and expectations for code to ensure that new functionalities do not compromise previous implementations.

LATENT will follow an **open contribution model**, where contributions can be made via GitHub pull requests. Contribution guidelines (e.g., via a CONTRIBUTING.md file) will outline how to submit patches, report issues, and participate in discussions. The core development will be overseen by both the main applicant and co-applicant, who will review contributions and maintain the overall coherence and quality of the codebase.

We think that this governance model will support community engagement while ensuring solid code-updates and software integrity.

7. How will your software be tested?

Each function and module will be accompanied by **tests** that verify expected outputs for known inputs. These tests will cover both the R interface and the underlying C++ backend (e.g., estimation routines, gradient and Hessian calculations, optimization outputs). Testing will ensure:

- Correct model estimates for benchmark datasets.
- Proper handling of boundary conditions and missing values.
- Accurate results across various latent variable model types.

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Also, LATENT will be validated against results and outputs from other established software (e.g., Mplus, lavaan, LatentGold) to verify that the estimated parameters and fit indices are equivalent when models are specified identically.

In addition, automated testing will be set up using **GitHub Actions**, which will run the test suite on all supported operating systems (Linux, macOS, and Windows) whenever changes are pushed to the repository. This ensures compatibility and reproducibility across platforms.

Given LATENT's emphasis on speed, performance benchmarks will be included to monitor runtime and memory efficiency when handling big datasets. This will allow us to maintain our performance advantage as the codebase evolves.

8. How will you check that it respects the licences of libraries and dependencies it uses?

LATENT has a minimal set of dependencies, relying primarily on:

- **Rcpp** for seamless integration between R and C++.
- **data.table** for efficient data manipulation.
- **armadillo** for high-performance computing of linear algebra operations and decompositions.
- **lavaan**: for extracting the syntax of SEM models.

All these packages are licensed under the **GNU General Public License v3 (GPL-3)**, which is compatible with LATENT's own licensing. As LATENT will also be distributed under **GPL-3**, we fully comply with the requirements of these dependencies—most importantly, ensuring that LATENT remains **free and open-source**.

Of course, any new dependency added in the future will be carefully reviewed to ensure it is GPL-compatible. Moreover, we follow CRAN policies, which include automated checks on licensing compatibility before submission.

This process guarantees that LATENT adheres to open-source legal standards while promoting transparent and ethical software development practices.

9. How will your software be packaged and distributed?

LATENT will be packaged as a standard **R package**, following the guidelines set by **CRAN (The Comprehensive R Archive Network)**. This includes:

- A properly structured package directory with a DESCRIPTION file (declaring metadata, dependencies, and license),
- Namespace management through a NAMESPACE file,
- Manual pages for each function (.Rd files), Vignettes and tutorial documents (vignettes/ directory) for in-depth examples and model walkthroughs.

Regarding the distribution of LATENT, it will be available from two sources:

- **CRAN**: Stable releases will be submitted to CRAN to ensure easy installation and long-term visibility within the R ecosystem. CRAN also performs rigorous checks across platforms (Windows, Linux, macOS), which guarantees compatibility and reliability. Code example to install LATENT from CRAN (in progress):
`install.packages("latent")`
- **GitHub**: Development versions will be hosted on GitHub (<https://github.com/Marcosjnez/latent>) to allow users early access to new features and to foster community contributions. GitHub will also serve as the platform for issue tracking, documentation updates, and community discussions. Code example to install LATENT from GitHub:
`devtools::install_github("Marcosjnez/latent")`

10. What level of support will be provided for users of the software and how will this support be organised?

LATENT will provide **multiple levels of user support** to ensure accessibility and usability for researchers with varying levels of expertise.

First, we will provide online documentation and tutorials. A full PDF manual will be available from the GitHub repository and the R's built-in help system whereas online tutorials and vignettes covering typical use cases, advanced models, and troubleshooting tips will be available from the webpage of the package. These resources will guide users to apply the functions of the package independently and resolve common issues.

Second, the GitHub repository and Discourse forum will be used to report bugs or technical problems, request new features, and ask questions about usage. This public forum encourages knowledge sharing, transparency, and community-based troubleshooting. Issues will be regularly reviewed and addressed by the development team of LATENT. Moreover, the **Discourse's platform** will serve as the main hub for support, feedback, and **collaborative decision-making**. This way, other researchers can collaborate on LATENT by making requests and direct **contributions –rewarded by co-authorship–** that we will moderate for appropriate development. This will turn LATENT into a **community-owned tool**.

Third, we plan to publish academic papers and tutorial articles demonstrating the use of LATENT in applied settings. These will serve as long-term references and teaching resources. We also aim to present the package at workshops and conferences related to open science, methodology, and R development, providing live demos and support.

11. How do you plan to ensure long term maintenance of your software?

We are committed to ensuring the **long-term sustainability and maintenance** of LATENT beyond the initial funding period. Even with no financial support, the intention of the development has always been to develop a free, open-source software that meets the increasing demands of current research. Because LATENT is also the central topic of the co-applicant's PhD, LATENT will remain the main research tool for developing and publishing new statistical methods.

LATENT is designed with a modular C++ backend and a well-structured R interface, which makes it easier to maintain and extend in the future. This structure enables independent development of new models and methods without affecting the stability of the core codebase. Furthermore, by hosting LATENT on GitHub, we aim to build an active contributor community. Clear contribution guidelines, issue tracking, and transparency will help attract external collaborators and foster shared responsibility for future development.

Also, LATENT will be aligned with the broader lavaan ecosystem not only with respect to the syntax for specifying models but also by mimicking the outputs that lavaan provides. This compatibility enhances the likelihood of continued relevance and support from the statistical programming community. In fact, this feature makes possible to use LATENT with other R packages from the lavaan ecosystem, such as semTools and tidySEM.

Finally, we will seek additional funding opportunities (e.g., Veni) to support further development. Collaborations with other research teams that actively use LATENT may also serve as a source of funding, as they may be willing to invest in the implementation of features aligned with their methodological needs.

This multi-pronged approach ensures that LATENT will remain a reliable, up-to-date, and impactful tool for researchers, aligned with the goals of open and sustainable science.

Section 6: References

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Section 7: Declaration

By submitting this form, I declare that:

- I and all the individuals involved in this proposal satisfy the nationally and internationally accepted standards for scientific conduct as stated in the Netherlands [Code of Conduct for Research Integrity](#) (The Universities of the Netherlands).
- The research organisation has been informed of this grant application and the research organisation accepts the grant conditions of this programme.
- I have completed this application form truthfully.
- I have submitted a pre-proposal for this Call for proposals in ISAAC.